

Methanation Catalyst for Low CO Concentration

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Abstract : A Ni-based catalyst supported by γ -Al₂O₃ was prepared by impregnation method, and the catalyst was used in a low CO and CO₂ concentration methanation system. The effect of temperature, pressure and space velocity on the methanation reaction was investigated in an experimental fixed-bed reactor. The methanation reaction was operated at the conditions of 190-240°C, 3000-24000ml•g⁻¹•h⁻¹ and 1.5-3.5MPa. The results show that temperature and space velocity play important role on the reaction. With the increase of reaction temperature the CO and CO₂ conversion increase and the selectivity of CH₄ increase. And with the increase of the space velocity the conversion of CO and CO₂ and the selectivity of CH₄ decrease sharply.

Keywords : coke oven gas, methanation, catalyst, fixed bed, performance

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